

PARADIGM Fast Plutonium Critical Experiment Neutron Noise Results

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ABSTRACT

We analyzed five critical configurations of Pu fuel from the Zero Power Physics Reactor (ZPPR) Plates with a copper reflector and the measured the prompt neutron decay constant α for each system. The systems were designed to maximize sensitivity to cross section information in the 30-600 keV energy range. The experiment was simulated using MCNP6.3. Using both a Rossi- α method and a Feynman- α method we estimated α for all five configurations, and found good agreement between the methods. Bootstrapping was applied for both methods to quantify the uncertainty. A comparison of the simulated delayed critical α_{DC} of $20983s^{-1}$ and the extrapolated α_{DC} of $20228s^{-1}$ from the measured α values plotted over inverse count rate was also reported and shows excellent agreement.

Keywords: Rossi- α , Feynman variance-to-mean, Neutron noise, Plutonium metal, Organic scintillator, Fast neutron detection

1. INTRODUCTION

Intermediate energy neutron interactions have long posed a challenge for nuclear data [1]. The inherent challenges of designing an experiment to maximize sensitivity to this region has resulted in there being far fewer benchmarks relevant to this region than either fast or thermal systems [2]. The Parallel Approach of Differential and Integral Measurements (PARADIGM) experiments are a collaborative effort to reduce the uncertainties in the nuclear data specifically for intermediate energies by parallelizing the nuclear data pipeline to evaluate differential and integral experiments designed cohesively to address specific uncertainties in intermediate energies. As part of this effort two critical configurations, a “fast” system and an “intermediate” system, were designed and conducted at the National Criticality Research Experiments Center (NCERC) as integral experiments using the Zero Power Physics Reactor (ZPPR) Plutonium No-Nickel Aluminum plates [3] as fuel with a large copper reflector [4]. This paper will focus on the results of the faster system.

Neutron noise analysis is a powerful validation tool for integral experiments that directly measures the prompt neutron decay constant α for steady state systems by measuring the statistical fluctuations in neutrons emitted from a multiplying system [5]. This is ideal for subcritical configurations where direct measurement of the multiplication factor k_{eff} is impossible and can be applied with high fidelity in delayed critical configurations. Estimation of α for comparison with simulation relies on the minimal influence of the detector's timing resolution and response. We used the Rossi Alpha Measurements – Rapid Organic (n,γ) Discrimination Detector (RAM-RODD) [6], an array of 8 EJ-309 organic scintillator detectors at NCERC to perform these measurements. RAM-RODD was dually optimized for spectroscopy and a sub-nanosecond timing resolution and benefits in these applications from a scatter-based detection mechanism that requires no moderation for neutrons.

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2. PARADIGM ASSEMBLY DESCRIPTION

The faster assembly of PARADIGM is designed to target the 30-600 keV energy range. An image of the physical set up is shown in Figure 1a with the fuel withdrawn from the assembly on the cylindrical plate. A rendering of the simulation in critical configuration is shown in Figure 1b fully closed. To match the desired spectra, the fast configuration makes use of no additional moderator plates and uses only the alumina trays shown in cyan in Figure 1b. These alumina trays are 0.58 inches tall with a recess cut out to enable two layers of ZPPR plates to be slotted. The critical configuration is made of 9 layers of fuel trays, 5 full ones on the top and 3 fully filled on the bottom. The 4th layer on the bottom stack has 16 fuel plates in it compared to the fully filled ones with 40. In all, 336 ZPPR plates were used. Around the assembly stack is a series of concentric copper reflectors used in previous experiments, particularly Jupiter and Zeus [4]. Neutronic modeling of the assembly was done post experiment as part of a final deliverable related to nuclear data adjustment of ^{239}Pu . The model includes air gaps, compositional impurities, room, and critical assembly machine.

(a) Experimental Fast Configuration Assembled

(b) Simulation of Fast Configuration with Labels

Figure 1. Experimental and simulated reconstruction of the Fast Configuration

3. SIMULATED α_{DC}

Simulation of α at delayed critical was performed using the KOPT card in MCNP6.3 and cross sections from the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library. To ensure well converged statistics the models were ran for 1000 active cycles each with 100,000 neutrons histories. This produced an uncertainty on k_{eff} to be 0.00002. The simulation results from the KOPT run are presented in Table I. In addition to ENDF/B-VIII.0, simulations with ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data library were ran to see if there was an observable difference. No parameters besides k_{eff} had a change outside of Monte-Carlo statistics.

Table I. Simulated Values of Rossi-Alpha and Other KOPTS Outputs

Quantity	Estimate	Std. Dev.
Generation Time (nsec)	101.50658	0.15406
Rossi-Alpha (/nsec)	-2.09826E-05	8.80787E-08
β_{eff}	0.00213	0.00001

4. NEUTRON NOISE MEASUREMENTS

The measurements were performed using RAM-RODD, an array of eight EJ-309 detectors optimized for spectroscopy and timing. RAM-RODD has a timing resolution of $\sim 900ps$, ideal for high precision neutron noise measurements of fast, high flux systems.

The experiment was performed on Comet, a vertical lift critical machine at NCERC with the fuel and inner reflector system being raised into the outer reflector. We measured and analyzed five configurations with the number of ZPPR plates ranging from 330 to 336. Configurations 330, and 333-335 were all measured with the system at full closure, and 336 was measured with a slight separation as an approximate delayed critical measurement. The detectors were 2.503 meters off the ground and on average approximately 1.4 meters from the center of the copper reflector.

5. NEUTRON NOISE ANALYSIS METHODS

Neutron noise applications rely on the point reactor kinetic equations for the estimation of α , the first eigenvalue of the time dependent transport equation and is defined as:

$$\alpha = \frac{\beta_{eff} - \rho}{\Lambda} \quad (1)$$

where β_{eff} is the effective delayed neutron fraction, ρ is the reactivity, and Λ is the prompt generation time. Two prominent methods of obtaining α from these equations are the Rossi- α and the Feynman- α methods.

5.1. Rossi- α Method

The Rossi- α method uses time correlations of fission radiation (neutron or gamma) to estimate the prompt neutron decay constant of a multiplying system. The method is detailed in [7–9] and is briefly summarized here. The prompt neutron decay constant is defined as

$$\alpha = \frac{1 - k_p}{l} \quad (2)$$

where k_p is the prompt multiplication factor and l is the prompt neutron lifetime. The prompt neutron lifetime is the average time a prompt neutron exists in the system before a terminating event. The prompt neutron population (N) following the injection of neutrons into a multiplying assembly decays with a dependence on α as

$$N = N_0 e^{-\alpha t} \quad (3)$$

where t is time and N_0 is the population at $t = 0$. Reactivity (ρ) is defined in terms of α as

$$\rho = \frac{k_{eff} - 1}{k_{eff}} = \beta_{eff} - \alpha\Lambda \quad (4)$$

where β_{eff} is the effective delayed neutron fraction, and Λ is the prompt neutron generation time. Λ is related to the prompt neutron life time, l , by $\Lambda = l/k_{eff}$.

The difference between the time of interaction of all neutron events within a given time window for a multiplying assembly is described by the probability density function

$$p(t)dt = Ae^{-\alpha t}dt + Bdt \quad (5)$$

where $Ae^{-\alpha t}$ describes the decay of the prompt neutron population and B describes the uniform accidental coincidence probability. Equation 5 is fit to the time difference distribution measured for an assembly near critical to estimate α .

We applied the Rossi- α method using a rolling-window technique where the time difference between the first event and all subsequent events recorded in a given time reset window was taken. The reset window was then shifted to the second recorded event, and the time difference between that event and all subsequent events within the reset window was calculated. This operation was performed until the end of the measured data was reached. Rephrased, let $t_{i=1}^N$ be the time-sorted measured events where $t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_N$. The differences $\Delta t = t_{i+j} - t_i, 1 \leq j \leq N_r$ were calculated where i is the index of the first event within a time reset window, t_r , and N_r is the index of the last event in t_r . This is repeated for all t_i in $t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_N$ where $t_N - t_i \geq t_{i+N_r}$. The time differences were histogrammed, and α was estimated by fitting Equation (5) to the time-difference histograms.

Our Rossi- α fit for the 336 configuration is shown in Figure 2 with the residuals of the fit plotted below.

Figure 2. Rossi- α distribution for 336 ZPPR plate configuration. The fit residuals are plotted below the distribution.

5.2. Feynman- α Method

The Feynman- α method or Feynman variance-to-mean method utilizes the excess variance in multiplying systems, as compared to a random Poisson process, to infer kinetics parameters of the system [7,10]. This excess variance is defined as

$$Y(t) = \frac{\overline{c(t)^2} - \overline{c(t)}^2}{\overline{c(t)}} - 1 \quad (6)$$

where $c(t)$ is the number of counts in a measurement gate of length t . The excess variance then saturates as the measurement gate length increases with a saturating exponential characteristic related to α by the following:

$$Y(t) = A \left(1 - \frac{1 - e^{-\alpha t}}{\alpha t} \right) \quad (7)$$

where A is the amplitude of the asymptote. We can estimate α by taking repeated measurements of the system at a given length window and computing Y and then repeating this process for many different gate lengths and fitting the saturating exponential behavior. We implemented a sequential non-overlapping gate structure for the Feynman- α analysis

5.3. Uncertainty Quantification: Bootstrapping

The precise quantification of uncertainty in neutron noise is difficult to achieve with analytic methods due to a number of factors. The fundamental assumptions of first order uncertainty propagation of linearity and independence of variables are both violated. Additionally, in the measurement and analysis, the system is treated as steady state which at or very near delayed critical may not be true. This leads to an underestimated uncertainty. We instead bootstrap the data stream to achieve a more robust characterization of uncertainty [11]. By sampling with replacement from our time information, we construct new instances of the measurement which are then analyzed and give an estimate of the parameter of interest. This is then repeated many times and a histogram of these estimates is constructed. Figure 3 shows this process for Feynman- α and Figure 4 shows this for Rossi- α

Figure 3. Illustration of Bootstrapping Y_2 and the Feynman- α fit on delayed critical configuration 336. The left plot shows the spread of the Y_2 values from the bootstrap which is then used as the 95% confidence interval for the respective Y_2 value on the fit to the right.

Figure 4. (a) Bootstrapped distribution for 10000 iterations of the Rossi- α distribution and (b) convergence plot for the 10000 iterations using the difference of the 95% confidence interval for the 334 ZPPR plate configuration.

6. RESULTS

The results of these measurements are reported in Table II with the uncertainties estimated by our bootstrapping methods.

Table II. Estimated α values in inverse seconds for the different configurations using Feynman and Rossi methods. Configuration 336 was measured without full closure.

Number of ZPPR Plates	Feynman- α (s^{-1})	Rossi- α (s^{-1})
330	75402 ± 1573	81410 ± 14887
333	45107 ± 208	45741 ± 1988
334	35639 ± 147	35024 ± 1116
335	26348 ± 110	26983 ± 254
336*	24750 ± 201	25969 ± 876

Figure 5 shows the linear extrapolation of α with decreasing inverse count rate to estimate α_{DC} . Our extrapolated value for α_{DC} from our fit is $20228s^{-1}$. This is in very good agreement with the simulated value from Table I of $20983s^{-1}$.

Figure 5. Estimated α versus inverse count rate and extrapolated α_{DC} . Estimated α_{DC} is 20228 and simulated α_{DC} is 20983.

The two noise methods of Rossi- α and Feynman- α produced comparable results, with Feynman having lower uncertainty values due to its suppression of the high accidental coincidence rate present in the system. The prediction interval in Figure 5 is calculated using the uncertainty analysis described in section 5.3 and the linear regression of the extrapolation. Configuration 330 was omitted from the linear fit for Figure 5 due to the configuration's large uncertainty.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we described and reported measurements of five subcritical and delayed critical configurations of copper reflected Pu fuel from the ZPPR Plates and the observed α for each system. The systems were designed to target specific cross section information in the 30-600 keV energy range. The delayed critical configuration of 336 ZPPR plates was simulated using MCNP6.3. We implemented both Rossi- α and Feynman- α methodologies, and we bootstrapped our time information to perform a robust uncertainty analysis of our results. The two methods generated comparable results. We also presented the linear extrapolation of α versus inverse count rate to estimate an α_{DC} of $20228s^{-1}$ and compared this to our simulated α_{DC} of $20983s^{-1}$.

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